

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER

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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

WP No	Del. Rel. No	Del No	Title	Lead beneficiary
4	D4.3	D23	Networking Event for Early Career Researchers #3	CU

Nature	Dissemination Level	Related to Del. No (if applicable)
Other	Public	

Description (short)
<p>The ENLIGHT “Research and Innovation Agenda with and for Society” (RISE) project aims at establishing foundations and initiating implementation of a joint research and innovation (R&I) agenda within the <u>ENLIGHT European University Alliance</u>.</p> <p>Work package 4 includes two specific projects. The first project, 4.1, involves planning a series of events to support networking and leadership skills for early career researchers (ECRs). The second project, 4.2, is the Researcher Assessment working group.</p> <p>On Tuesday, April 30th, 2024, the third event related to work package 4.1 took place from 10:00 to 14:30 CET. The event, titled "Five Commonalities of High Performing Teams," was conducted online. The guest presenter was Dr. Juko-Mart Kõlar from the University of Tartu.</p>

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1. Project background

As outlined in the project description ENLIGHT RISE aims to *'enable a world-class joint R&I agenda within ENLIGHT RISE we will need to ATTRACT AND RETAIN THE BEST RESEARCHERS in Europe and beyond, while promoting an inclusive leadership culture in keeping with the broader mission of ENLIGHT'*.

Work Package 4 is led by Comenius University Bratislava (CU), with co-leads Ghent University and the University of Galway. The aim is to develop attractive career frameworks for researchers by implementing networking, mentoring, and leadership training initiatives within the alliance, as well as explore innovative solutions to modernise researcher assessment in order to better reward diverse and engaged career paths.

ENLIGHT's key objective is to establish a balanced network across various social, economic, and geographic areas in Europe, emphasizing the sharing of expertise and opportunities. Additionally, the alliance aims to create a supportive structure for talent development, career guidance, and business ideas.

ENLIGHT RISE focuses on nurturing its human capital as a fundamental element for a competitive joint R&I agenda. Expanding on the ENLIGHT Erasmus+ project's skills workshops for the doctoral network, the initiative has extended to form a network of early career researchers (post-docs, early career faculty, <10 yrs. from PhD.) to facilitate research collaborations on the ENLIGHT flagship challenges and encourage research mobility.

The first two events occurred at the end of October 2022 and mid-June 2023, respectively.

2. Event Planning

The insights gained from the two initial events led to scheduling a second event in April 2024. This timeframe was chosen to ensure maximum appeal. Moreover, to promote synergies and improve visibility, we have co-scheduled the event for early career researchers with the WP1 matchmaking event, D1.7 and D1.8, respectively.

As is customary for event planning, the team leader and co-leaders of the working group discussed various topics and options for the upcoming event. After consulting with members from the other partner universities, decisions were made regarding:

- Hold the event online;
- Date of event: 30th April 2024;
- Topic – “Five Commonalities of High Performing Teams”;
- Duration of event – 4,5 hours (with breaks);
- Communications strategy;
- Presenter – agreed that WP lead would source the speaker;
- Registration/event management/feedback etc. – was agreed to be managed by Comenius University Bratislava.

Doctor Juko-Mart Kõlar, University of Tartu, was identified by the leads from Comenius, Galway, and Ghent as the most suitable guest speaker. A registration portal was created, and the event was held using MS Teams.

WP4 and WP1 partners held several meetings to discuss and agree on communication methods. It was decided that the event's registration forms would be handled separately, while the dissemination and promotion would be managed mutually in a synchronized manner. All attendees of the meetings had the opportunity to ask any questions they had. It was decided that PhD researchers could attend WP 4.1 events, as R1 was the most significant group represented during our first two networking events. We also considered topics from past feedback forms.

3. Communications/Promotion

The ENLIGHT communications team promoted the event via the ENLIGHT website, calendar, and social media channels. <https://enlight-eu.org/index.php/university-about-us/news-events/158-news/1121-workshop-for-early-career-researchers-five-commonalities-of-high-performing-teams>

Universities were responsible for their internal promotion of the event.

Reminders were sent to the partner universities to further disseminate the event in the week preceding the event.

An event reminder was sent to all those registered the day before the event.

4. Speaker

Doctor Juko-Mart Kõlar is a Director at the University of Tartu Viljandi Culture Academy, the largest regional university college in Estonia. He is a lecturer of “Creative Entrepreneurship” and “Business Model Innovation”. Since 2010, he has supervised over 2,000 teams in various universities and business programs. He defended his doctoral thesis (“The Emerging Patterns of Digitalization in the Estonia Music Industry”) at Estonian Business School in 2019 and he has co-founded two technology companies in the music industry. He is also a former Board Member of the Estonian Authors’ Society and an Advisor on Music at the Estonian Ministry of Culture.

Doctor Juko-Mart Kõlar offered a practical case study on navigating the complexities of building and managing a diverse team in a fiercely competitive landscape. He outlined strategies and techniques for fostering an environment where every team member comprehends their role in achieving objectives and where efficient coordination mechanisms are ingrained in the daily culture.

5. Event Data

Registrations by 30th April 2024

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UPV/EHS	UBx	CU	NUI GALWAY	UGent	UGOE	RUG	UT	Bern	Other*
5	10	25	3	13	10	13	31	3	8

* Other: People who registered using personal email accounts and didn't specify university choice.

Attendees on 14th June 2023

As per the initial MS Teams report **75** was the maximum number of attendees who attended the online event (as per unique IDs). There were some last-minute cancellation notices and requests for the recording post-event. The event was attended by PhD researchers, postdoctoral researchers, research fellows, professional support staff, and other academic positions. The chat during the sessions was very active.

Event schedule:

10:00 – 10:05 CET	Opening introductions/allowing time for people to join/request to record the event
10:05 – 10:10 CET	Brief introduction of ENLIGHT and Juko-Mart Kõlar by organizer
10:10 – 11:00 CET	Juko-Mart Kõlar, Session I of leadership training and networking for ECRs
11:00 – 11:30 CET	Break
11:30 – 12:30 CET	Juko-Mart Kõlar, Session II of leadership training and networking for ECRs
12:30 – 13:30 CET	Lunch break
13:30 – 14:15 CET	Juko-Mart Kõlar, Session III of leadership training and networking for ECRs
14:15 – 14:25 CET	Discussion and Q&A
14:25 – 14:30 CET	Closing comments

6. Feedback post-event

Participants were sent the event materials along with the feedback form/link after the event.

Eleven responses were received, which accounted for over 14% of attendees. The attendees were asked the following questions:

To which university do you belong?

UPV/EHS	CU	NUI GALWAY	UGent	UT
1	5	1	1	3

To which job area/title do you most closely align?

PhD Researcher	Postdoctoral Researcher	Research Fellow	Professional support staff	Academic staff
4	1	2	2	2

Gender.

Woman	Man
9	2

On a scale of 1 to 5 (5 being the highest), how would you rate this workshop?

5	4	3	2	1
6	4	1	-	-

With an average score of 4,4.

List 1-3 things you found most useful about this event.

The team received 10 replies of feedback regarding the question of what you “found most useful about this event”. The experience was the most popular aspect, followed by the depth of knowledge and the practical insights.

What do you think could have made this event better?

There were 8 replies to this question, with most respondents indicating that everything was satisfactory. However, a few individuals requested a shorter/longer format for the event.

7. Recommendations and lessons learned.

The event aimed to bring together diverse perspectives and share experiences on supporting early career researchers in academia. The awareness-raising campaigns, stakeholder communication, and personal online meetings were successful in generating the expected feedback. The highlight of the campaign was the invitation of Dr. Juko-Mart Kõlar from the University of Tartu Viljandi Culture Academy, who shared his professional career journey with early career researchers, including PhD researchers, post-docs, and early career faculty researchers as a guest speaker.

Individual outreach through personal contacts or recommendations, followed by personal online meetings, proved to be the most effective approach. The main goal was to identify relevant stakeholders and discuss potential collaboration on projects in the realm of attractive career pathways for researchers.

Appendix 1 – Designing Your Life template

Life One: That Thing You Do

Six-word headline describing the essence of it: Vedeckovýskumný zamestnanec, vysokoškolský pedagóg, projektový manažér

1	2	3	4	5
<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.</p>	<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.</p>	<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.</p>	<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.</p>	<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.</p>

Questions to ask:

1. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet
2. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet
3. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet

Resources
time, money,
skill, contacts

Likability
are you hot
or cold?

Confidence
are you confident
or uncertain?

Coherence
is it consistent
with you?

Life Two: That Thing You'd Do If Thing One Were Suddenly Gone

Six-word headline describing the essence of it: Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet

1	2	3	4	5
<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.</p>	<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.</p>	<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.</p>	<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.</p>	<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.</p>

Questions to ask:

1. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet
2. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet
3. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet

Resources
time, money,
skill, contacts

Likability
are you hot
or cold?

Confidence
are you confident
or uncertain?

Coherence
is it consistent
with you?

Life Three: The Thing You'd Do or the Life You'd Live If Money or Image Were No Object

Six-word headline describing the essence of it: Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet

1	2	3	4	5
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.

Questions to ask:

1. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet
2. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet
3. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet

Resources
time, money, skill, contacts

Likability
are you hot or cold?

Confidence
are you confident or uncertain?

Coherence
is it consistent with you?

Appendix 2 – Role matrix template

<p>True strengths <i>Experienced, good at it, like it</i></p> <p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Morbi a ornare elit. Vestibulum quam nisi, volutpat ut porta lobortis, aliquet nec nunc. Donec mollis, enim non dictum luctus, magna ex vestibulum sem, sed tincidunt velit mi vitae odio. Sed ut luctus turpis. Sed accumsan sem vitae lobortis porta. Praesent gravida eros quis arcu tempor pulvinar. Phasellus condimentum eu leo id scelerisque.</p>	<p>Non-strength likes <i>Limited experience or talent, but like it</i></p> <p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Morbi a ornare elit. Vestibulum quam nisi, volutpat ut porta lobortis, aliquet nec nunc. Donec mollis, enim non dictum luctus, magna ex vestibulum sem, sed tincidunt velit mi vitae odio. Sed ut luctus turpis. Sed accumsan sem vitae lobortis porta. Praesent gravida eros quis arcu tempor pulvinar. Phasellus condimentum eu leo id scelerisque.</p>
<p>Strength dislikes <i>Lot of experience, but don't like it</i></p> <p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Morbi a ornare elit. Vestibulum quam nisi, volutpat ut porta lobortis, aliquet nec nunc. Donec mollis, enim non dictum luctus, magna ex vestibulum sem, sed tincidunt velit mi vitae odio. Sed ut luctus turpis. Sed accumsan sem vitae lobortis porta. Praesent gravida eros quis arcu tempor pulvinar. Phasellus condimentum eu leo id scelerisque.</p>	<p>Shortcomings <i>Little or no experience, do it poorly, hate it</i></p> <p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Morbi a ornare elit. Vestibulum quam nisi, volutpat ut porta lobortis, aliquet nec nunc. Donec mollis, enim non dictum luctus, magna ex vestibulum sem, sed tincidunt velit mi vitae odio. Sed ut luctus turpis. Sed accumsan sem vitae lobortis porta. Praesent gravida eros quis arcu tempor pulvinar. Phasellus condimentum eu leo id scelerisque.</p>

Appendix 3 – Team canvas template

